

Optimizing Radiographic Practices and Anxiety Management in Pediatric Dentistry: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract -Pediatric dental radiography is indispensable for detecting carious lesions, developmental anomalies, and other oral pathologies that may not be clinically evident. However, obtaining diagnostic-quality radiographs in children poses significant challenges due to behavioural factors, dental anxiety, anatomical limitations, and exaggerated gag reflexes. This comprehensive review evaluates literature from 2001 to 2024, focusing on optimizing radiographic techniques and anxiety management in pediatric dentistry. Non-pharmacological behaviour guidance methods—such as tell-show-do, desensitization, distraction using audio-visual aids, euphemistic language, and parental presence—play a pivotal role in enhancing patient cooperation and minimizing psychological distress. Pharmacological interventions, including sedation, are indicated for patients who remain uncooperative despite basic strategies. Technical adaptations such as using smaller film sizes, positioning devices, bent film techniques, and extraoral imaging further improve patient comfort and diagnostic outcomes. Effective gag reflex management through psychological diversion and topical agents facilitates radiographic procedures in sensitive patients. Additionally, individualized radiation protection protocols and the adoption of digital imaging technologies reduce unnecessary exposure. Integrating tailored behavioural guidance with advanced radiographic practices enhances diagnostic efficiency, patient safety, and overall treatment outcomes. This review underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary, child-centred approach to achieve optimal radiographic care in pediatric dentistry.

Keywords: *Pediatric Dentistry, radiography dental, behaviour management, anxiety management, radiology and pediatric dentistry, behaviour management and pediatric dentistry.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Pediatric dental radiography is an essential diagnostic tool that complements clinical examination and medical history to detect dental caries, developmental anomalies, and other oral pathologies that may not be visible otherwise.¹⁻³ However, obtaining high-quality radiographs in children is uniquely challenging due to behavioural factors, anxiety, and technical limitations associated with the smaller anatomy of infants, children, and adolescents.⁴⁻⁶ Managing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that integrates effective behaviour guidance techniques with tailored radiographic methods to ensure diagnostic accuracy while minimizing psychological distress and radiation exposure.⁷ Over the past two decades, advancements in non-pharmacological and pharmacological behaviour management strategies, along with innovations in imaging technology, have significantly improved pediatric patient cooperation and safety.⁸ This review critically examines the literature, focusing on behaviour management and radiographic techniques in pediatric dentistry, highlighting best practices and emerging trends to optimize patient care.

II. METHOD

This paper examines the literature spanning from 2001 to 2024. An electronic search was carried out in databases including MEDLINE/PubMed, EBSCOhost, Scopus and Google Scholar, using keywords such as “radiology and pediatric dentistry,” “behaviour management and pediatric dentistry” and “pediatric dentistry”. Additionally, information was manually collected from the textbooks. Certain recommendations were influenced by the knowledge and expertise of seasoned researchers and clinicians.

III. DISCUSSION

Obtaining diagnostic quality radiographs in pediatric patients presents unique challenges due to behavioural factors and technical constraints associated with treating infants, children, and adolescents.¹ Radiographs are an essential diagnostic tool, forming the foundation of accurate diagnosis and treatment planning alongside a thorough medical history and clinical examination.⁹ They are crucial because visual examination alone may fail to detect issues such as proximal tooth decay, infections of the teeth and bones, and the state of developing permanent teeth etc.^{5,10,11}

The primary goal of pediatric radiology techniques and patient management is to obtain these necessary diagnostic radiographs while ensuring maximum comfort and minimum psychological trauma for the patient and eliminating unnecessary repeated radiographic exposure.

Behaviour Guidance and Anxiety Assessment

Successful treatment of pediatric dental patients relies on effective communication and developing customized behaviour guidance plans tailored to the patient's needs and the dentist's skills.^{12,13}

A major concern in pediatric dentistry is Dental fear and anxiety, which can result in uncooperative behaviour that impedes the efficient delivery and quality of dental care, potentially acting as a barrier to routine care in the future.^{5,14,15} Stimuli such as the sight of the anesthetic needle and the sound of the drill are particularly fear-inducing. However, radiological imaging itself, involving unfamiliar equipment, radiation exposure concerns, and prior negative experiences, can also heighten anxiety.⁵

Various methods are used to assess anxiety in pediatric patients, including behavioural assessment, psychometric questionnaires, and analysis of physiological responses. The latter includes measuring pulse rate, blood oxygen levels, and body temperature. Salivary cortisol is a validated biological marker for detecting dental anxiety, as this enzyme is released in higher quantities during stressful situations. Venham Picture Test (VPT) / Venham Picture Scale, Facial Image Scale (FIS), Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale etc, are the scales used for the evaluation of the anxiety of the patient.

In one study examining the effect of a thematic approach during dental radiology, no significant differences were observed between thematic and standard environments regarding pulse rate, oxygen levels, or body temperature. However, post-procedure salivary cortisol levels were significantly lower in the thematically designed environment group, indicating a reduction in physiological stress.¹⁶

Behaviour guidance is a continual process spanning from basic to advanced techniques, incorporating both non-pharmacological and pharmacological options.

Behaviour Management Techniques

Non-pharmacological strategies are commonly employed to shape a child's behaviour, build trust, and instil positive dental attitudes.^{3,6,7} The AAPD lists several basic techniques, including verbal and non-verbal communication, behaviour shaping (modification) which includes desensitization, modelling and contingency management, and behaviour guidance which includes distraction, biofeedback, voice control, hypnosis, humor, coping, relaxation, implosive therapy and aversive conditioning.¹⁷

Pharmacological methods of behaviour management include premedication which includes sedatives and hypnotics, antianxiety drugs, antihistamines, conscious sedation.

Use of Euphemisms

Euphemisms are the substitute words, which can be used in presence of children as the choice of words by the dentists or staff influence the emotional status of the child. Therefore, the use of euphemisms is very important while addressing the child. It involves explaining the procedure using age-appropriate language, such as referring to the radiographic film as a “tooth picture” and the X-ray head as a “tooth camera” in the context of radiology.¹⁸

Tell-show-do (TSD) is a fundamental communicative guidance technique where the procedure is introduced stepwise: a verbal explanation (tell) is followed by a demonstration of the procedure's sensory aspects (show), and then the procedure is performed immediately (do). In the context of radiology, TSD The child may be allowed to touch and examine the film and equipment.^{14,17,18}

Desensitization Techniques: Desensitization is defined as gradually exposing the child to the experiences of increasing intensity. Obtaining the least difficult radiograph first (such as an anterior occlusal) desensitizes the child to the procedure.¹⁷⁻²⁰ Another example of desensitization is the “Lollipop Radiograph Technique.” The child is given a lollipop to lick (preferably sugarless), then after a few licks the lollipop is taken from the child and a radiographic film is attached to the lollipop with an orthodontic rubber band, and the child is asked to hold it while the exposure is made and the picture is taken.

Procuring posterior radiographs can be made more pleasant by associating it with a pleasurable taste, bubble gum. Before placing the radiograph in the patient's mouth apply bubble gum flavored toothpaste to the film.²⁰

Contingency management/Positive reinforcement like verbal praise and rewards like stickers or toys, is crucial for encouraging cooperative behaviour in a child patient.^{4,17}

Distraction Techniques involves diverting a patient's attention from a perceived unpleasant procedure. Audio-Visual Distraction (AVD) is highly effective for reducing anxiety. AVD is categorized as diverting attention using audio-visual means, often employing virtual reality (VR) eyeglasses, television screens, or computer screens.

Research comparing different AVD methods showed that ceiling-mounted AVD was the most effective in reducing anxiety in pediatric dental patients, followed by chair-mounted AVD. Audio distraction alone (e.g., popular songs through headphones) was the less effective technique than Audio-Visual Distraction. AVD techniques were found to significantly reduce anxiety, measured both subjectively (VPT) and objectively (pulse rate), particularly during stressful dental procedures.^{4,17,21}

In a study investigating a thematic approach (creating an environment with supportive design and positive distractions, such as space-themed wall murals in a radiology room), the thematic environment was linked to significantly reduced post-procedure salivary cortisol levels, suggesting its potential to influence neuroendocrine responses linked to stress.

Parental Presence/Absence

For very young patients (under three years of age) requiring a radiograph, it may be necessary for the child to sit in the parent's lap. Such positioning reduces the child's anxiety, provides additional emotional security for the child, increases cooperation and also enables the parent to adequately restrain child and avoid any unexpected sudden movements.

Correct settings are made on the apparatus and the x-ray head is properly positioned before placing the film in the child's mouth. The parent and the child should be adequately protected with lead aprons to reduce radiation exposure. If the child is uncooperative, then additional restraint by a second adult may be necessary. A positioning device such as a Snap-A-Ray can be used to aid the parent in positioning and securing the film.

A second adult stabilizes the child's head with one hand while the other hand positions the x-ray holder in the patient's mouth. If a second adult is not available, it may be necessary to place the child in a mechanical restraining device (Papoose Board) to adequately restrain the child.

If the child is still too uncooperative, it may be necessary to manage the child pharmacologically with inhalation, oral, or parental sedatives.

Dental practices should maintain flexible policies regarding parental presence/absence and make decisions on a case-by-case basis, prioritizing patient safety.²²⁻²⁴

Managing the Gag Reflex

Some patients, young and old, have an exaggerated gag reflex. The etiology of an exaggerated gag reflex had been attributed to psychological and physical factors.

Taking a radiograph for a child with exaggerated gag reflex can be challenging. The easiest is through diversion and positive suggestion. The operator suggests to the patient the gag reflex can be reduced by concentrating on something other than the procedure.

Some of the Psychological measures which can be used are: Pant like a dog, move the leg up and point a toe, place a small amount of salt on the tip of the tongue (distraction procedure).

Some of the pharmacological options are topical anesthetic agents, such as lidocaine spray, can be administered to produce temporary numbness, particularly of the soft palate and tongue. Nitrous oxide analgesia is an alternative that reduces the gag reflex

Bent film radiographic technique can be used in young children who cannot tolerate placement of film inside their mouth. Patient bite on the film that has a sharp right-angle bend at the top, bent part serves as a self-contained bite tab to hold the film in the place. The child is instructed to softly bite down to avoid cusp marks and distortion on the film.^{20,25}

Technical Adaptations while choosing the film

To overcome challenges posed by a child's small jaw or difficulty holding the film:

Film Size: Use the smallest film size available (size 0 film) for children with small mouths, followed by size 1 and size 2.

Film Positioning: Using a Snap-A-Ray positioning device can help secure the film. Positioning the radiograph vertically can reduce distal extension, which may increase tolerance, especially for patients with a mild gag reflex. A self-sticking sponge tab may also reduce impingement of the radiograph on the intraoral soft tissue.^{20,25}

Management of Uncooperative Patients (Protective Stabilization)

If a patient remains uncooperative despite basic behaviour guidance, advanced behaviour guidance techniques are necessary, including protective stabilization, sedation, or general anesthesia.

Protective stabilization involves the physical limitation of a patient's movement for a finite time by a person (active immobilization) or by restrictive equipment (passive immobilization). Devices like the Papoose Board® are full-body stabilization devices used for passive immobilization.

Indications for protective stabilization include:

The patient requires immediate diagnosis and/or urgent limited treatment but cannot cooperate due to developmental level, lack of maturity, or medical conditions.

Uncontrolled movements risk injury to the patient, parent, clinician, or staff.

Limited stabilization is needed for a sedated patient to reduce untoward movements. The patient has special health-care needs (SHCN) and exhibits movements that significantly interfere with the quality of care or pose harm.

Protective stabilization is contraindicated for cooperative, nonsedated patients or when treatment is non-emergent. It must never be used as a means of discipline, convenience, or retaliation.

Informed consent must be obtained and documented before utilizing protective stabilization. The practitioner must explain the benefits, risks, and alternatives (e.g., sedation, general anesthesia, deferred care). Continuous monitoring of the patient's physical and psychological well-being is mandatory, and stabilization must be terminated if the patient experiences severe emotional stress to prevent physical or psychological trauma. If a second adult is needed to restrain an uncooperative child during radiology, that adult should not be a staff member but rather a parent or another adult.

If non-pharmacological methods and protective stabilization fail, it may be necessary to manage the child pharmacologically with inhalation, oral, or parenteral sedatives. Advanced behavior guidance includes sedation and general anesthesia, each requiring parent's consent, evaluation of objectives, indications, contraindications, and precautions.^{17,18}

Radiation Safety and Exposure

The goal of pediatric radiology is to eliminate unnecessary repeated radiographic exposure. To protect patients and parents from radiation exposure, current radiation hygiene practices include using: the newer X-ray film or digital radiography to minimize radiation dose. A lead apron and thyroid collar to reduce body exposure. The highest film speed and largest film the child can tolerate. X-rays only on an individualized basis after clinical examination, not routinely.

For trauma cases, such as a tooth fracture with concurrent lip laceration, a soft tissue radiograph may be necessary to rule out tooth fragments embedded in the soft tissue; for this purpose, exposure time is reduced to one-fourth of the original exposure. Newer digital panoramic radiographic units (e.g., Planmeca Promax, Sirona Panorex) can take bitewing radiographs using extraoral techniques, which has shown better patient compliance, faster appointments, and less radiation than conventional intraoral radiographs while providing diagnostic quality images.^{23,24,26}

IV. CONCLUSION

Pediatric dental radiography requires a careful balance between obtaining diagnostic quality images and managing the unique behavioural challenges of children. This review emphasizes the importance of combining effective behaviour management techniques—such as tell-show-do, desensitization, distraction, and positive reinforcement—with technical adaptations like smaller film sizes and positioning aids to enhance patient comfort and cooperation. Non-pharmacological methods remain the first line of approach, while pharmacological sedation is reserved for cases where these techniques prove insufficient. Managing anxiety, the gag reflex, and ensuring parental involvement contribute to smoother procedures and better patient experiences. Additionally, protective stabilization, when used appropriately and with informed consent, can aid in handling uncooperative patients safely. Prioritizing radiation safety through modern technology and individualized imaging protocols minimizes exposure risks. Overall, integrating behavioural and technical strategies improves both the effectiveness of pediatric radiographic procedures and the child's psychological well-being, promoting positive attitudes toward dental care and supporting optimal oral health outcomes.

V. REFERENCES

1. McDonald RE, Avery DR, Dean JA. *McDonald and Avery's Dentistry for the Child and Adolescent*. 10th ed. St. Louis: Elsevier; 2016.
2. Pinkham JR, Casamassimo PS, Fields HW, McTigue DJ, Nowak AJ. *Pediatric Dentistry: Infancy through Adolescence*. 5th ed. St. Louis: Elsevier; 2013.
3. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Behavior guidance for the pediatric dental patient. *Pediatr Dent*. 2024;46(6):292-309.
4. Buchanan H, Niven N. Validation of a facial image scale to assess child dental anxiety. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2002;12(1):47-52.
5. Yücel G, Demir B, Smail FS, Sahinoglu S, Noyan U. The effect of a thematic environment on children's anxiety during intraoral radiography. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2025;35(1):103-110.
6. Majstorović M, Veerkamp JS, Skrinjarić I. Reliability and validity of measures of anxiety in 5–7-year-old children during dental treatment. *Eur J Paediatr Dent*. 2003;4(4):197-202.
7. Wright GZ, Kupietzky A. *Behavior Management in Dentistry for Children*. 2nd ed. Ames, IA: Wiley-Blackwell; 2014.
8. Klingberg G, Broberg AG. Dental fear/anxiety and dental behaviour management problems in children and adolescents: a review of prevalence and concomitant psychological factors. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2007;17(6):391-406.
9. Farman AG, Scarfe WC. The basics of maxillofacial cone beam computed tomography. *Semin Orthod*. 2009;15(1):2-13.
10. Koch G, Poulsen S, Espelid I, Haubek D. *Pediatric Dentistry: A Clinical Approach*. 3rd ed. Wiley-Blackwell; 2017.
11. American Dental Association Council on Scientific Affairs. The use of dental radiographs: update and recommendations. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2012;143(7):899-902.
12. Versloot J, Veerkamp JS, Hoogstraten J. Pain behaviour and distress in children during two sequential dental visits: comparing a computerised anaesthesia delivery system and a traditional syringe. *Br Dent J*. 2008;205(1):E2.
13. Veerkamp JS, Gruythuysen RJ. Anxiety reduction by nitrous oxide: a retrospective study of 1, 531 dental treatments. *ASDC J Dent Child*. 1998;65(2):91-96.
14. Venham LL, Bengston D, Cipes M. Children's response to sequential dental visits. *J Dent Res*. 1977;56(5):454-459.
15. Wong DL, Baker CM. Pain in children: comparison of assessment scales. *Pediatr Nurs*. 1988;14(1):9-17.
16. Gilman Yucel, Burcu Demir, Ferruh Semir Smail, Sureyya Sahinoglu, Ulku Noyan. Exploring the role of a thematic approach in dental anxiety and physiological stress: an investigation into dental radiology. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2025. 49(2);81-88.
17. Marwah N. *Textbook of Pediatric Dentistry*. 4th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers; 2019.
18. Tandon S. *Paediatric Dentistry*. 3rd ed. New Delhi: Paras Medical Publisher; 2018.
19. Kaira LS, Dabral E, Ray S, Kapoor P, Negi M. Management of gag reflex in children during intraoral radiography: a clinical review. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2020;30(4):385-392.
20. Thikkurissy S, Allen K, Smiley M, Casamassimo P, Kirk K. Children's response to topical anesthetics during radiographic film placement. *Pediatr Dent*. 2010;32(1):7-11.
21. Aminabadi NA, Erfanparast L, Sohrabi A, Oskouei SG, Naghili A. The impact of audiovisual distraction on pain and anxiety during dental treatment in 4–6 year-old children. *J Dent Res Dent Clin Dent Prospects*. 2012;6(4):117-124.
22. Rushton VE, Horner K, Worthington HV. The quality of panoramic radiographs in a sample of general dental practices. *Br Dent J*. 1999;186(12):630-633.
23. Ludlow JB, Davies-Ludlow LE, Brooks SL, Howerton WB. Dosimetry of 3 CBCT devices for oral and maxillofacial radiology: CB Mercuray, NewTom 3G and i-CAT. *Dentomaxillofac Radiol*. 2006;35(4):219-226.
24. European Commission. Radiation Protection No 172: Cone Beam CT for dental and maxillofacial radiology. Evidence based guidelines. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; 2012.
25. Guideline on protective stabilization for pediatric dental patients. *Pediatr Dent*. 2018;40(6):229-233.
26. American Academy of Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology. Clinical recommendations regarding use of cone beam computed tomography in orthodontics. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol*. 2013;116(2):238-257.